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AUDIT COMMITTEE CHARACTERISTICS ON EARNINGS MANAGEMENT OF LISTED INDUSTRIAL GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of audit committee characteristics on earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021. The number of industrial goods firms is fifteen (15), out of which nine (9) were used for analysis. The study seeks to examine the effect audit committee characteristics (as measured by audit committee financial expertise, audit committee meetings) have on earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The method of data collection for the study was secondary and data were extracted from sources, such as the sampled firms annual reports and accounts. The study uses STATA 13.0 as a tool for the data analysis. The results show that there is positive significant relationship between audit committee financial expertise, audit committee meetings and audit committee size on earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The research concludes that there is a positive and significant relationship between audit committee financial expertise and earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Audit committee meeting and earnings management of listed industrial products corporations in Nigeria have a positive and significant association. Finally, there is a positive and significant association between the firm size and the earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Leverage has a positive association with earnings management. The study recommends that listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria should engage experts audit members who have specific knowledge and expertise and also the corporations should hold regular meetings to oversee financial reporting process and internal control of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Also, the management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria should enhance the size of their firms since it has the ability to increase the earnings of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The firm should monitor its leverage since it can improve financial performance.

Keywords: Audit Committee, Audit Committee Meetings, Audit Committee Size, Earnings Management, Financial Expertise, Industrial Goods firms

Introduction

Globalisation and harsh competition have increased pressure on organizations to develop their effective corporate governance mechanism. This crisis arose as result of inherent conflicts of interest between Shareholders and corporate management. This contradiction involves the establishment of rules to govern the behavior of those involved in company management. Following the recent high-profile accounting scandals, investors have expressed an interest in the topic of quality financial reporting (Aderemi, 2019).

Earnings management occurs when executives use their judgment in financial reporting and transaction structuring to change financial reports in order to intentionally swindle some stakeholders about the company's fundamental financial performance or to influence contractual outcomes based on reported accounting figures (Almomani & Obeidat, 2013).

The audit committee's core commitment is to supervise the process of financial reporting and to examine managers' performance patterns that involve earnings manipulation (Yahaya, & Awen, 2021). In recent years, regulators have questioned the usefulness of audit committees in ensuring that financial statements are accurately stated and free of earnings management (Onyabe, et al., 2018). The audit committee's function in checking financial reporting has been reinforced by corporate governance in some nations as a result of the several company failures in certain industries (Hussaini & Gugong, 2015).

Audit committee members should also have specific knowledge and skills in financial reporting, auditing, and internal controls (Xie, 2017). To analyse the quality and integrity of financial accounts, audit committee members should have a solid understanding of accounting principles and financial reporting standards (such as Generally Accepted Accounting Principles or International Financial Reporting Standards). More Audit Committee meetings, according to Abbott (2016), are connected with fewer fines for deception and aggressive accounting. Previous studies have shown that the size of the Committee and the members' financial expertise can have a significant impact on earnings management monitoring, therefore having unconventional directors on the Audit Committee is beneficial. Earnings management, on the other hand, reduces required dependability and therefore its importance.

As result, if wages are to retain their relevance, strategies for improving the reporting of quality earnings must be developed. Following the global financial crisis of 2008, there is a rising need to look upward for evidence of earnings reliability. Corporate financial reporting failure has increased in recent decades, posing a severe dilemma for people who rely on this information. When the American energy business enron went bankrupt in 2001, the country became suspicious of window-dressed accounts. After reorganizing its finances, the company eventually declared bankruptcy. Auditing industrial products companies in Nigeria also necessitates auditors having a thorough understanding of the industry, its unique issues, and appropriate accounting and reporting standards. To properly address these audit challenges, auditors must maintain professional skepticism, practice due investigation, and stay current on industry advancements and legislative changes.

It is thought that analyzing the composition of audit committees and how companies in the industrial goods manufacturing industry handle their revenues is critical. As a result, high-profile controversies involving organisations such as Enron, Xerox, and WorldCom Regulators formal lover the world is becoming more cognizant of the supervisory role that audit committees play in the financial reporting process (Aderemi, 2019). Following the affair, financial markets lost faith in financial reporting, and market participants chastised the

accountants and auditors. Consequently, governments and regulatory agencies began to adopt increasingly stringent corporate regulation systems.

The Audit Committee is the most important of the oversight committees because it is responsible for reviewing both audited and unaudited financial accounts in order to ensure reliable reporting and reduce the likelihood of unethical or abusive accounting practices on the part of management (Hussaini & Gugong, 2015). Despite the existence of this watchdog, several enterprises have failed. Kraft Heinz Company Plc, Klynveld Peat Marwick Goerdeler, Granite Construction Company, Intercontinental Bank Plc, and Oceanic Bank are a few instances. The study would contribute to regulatory body such as the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX), Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and legislatures, in financial policies such as corporate government policies, regulations and implementations of rules on code of corporate governance, if need be, for improvement on overhaul and other lapses not address in 2018 code of corporate governance to attract and encourage foreign investors. Policy maker can use insight from this study to shape financial regulations and corporate governance commission.

The study would be of significant to future researchers who may be interested in studying corporate governance mechanisms and earnings management, it has advance previous study by providing theoretical, practically related variables on how the empirically affects each other, information are knowledge in making suggestions and references for future studies. Academics, on the other hand, can't seem to agree on whether audit committee features are related to earnings management.

Despite the fact that certain studies showed negative links, Beasley and Selterio, (2001) discovered positive relationships in similar works (Yang & Krishman, 2005; Lin, et al., 2006; Beasley & Salterio, 2001; Kuang & Sharma, 2013). Nonetheless, several studies produced contradictory results (Nelson & Jamil, 2012). However, the researcher finds that few studies in Nigeria have made an effort to explain the contrasting findings, especially in Nigerian registered industrial goods enterprises. This represents a lost opportunity. As such, this study investigates the effect of audit characteristics and earnings management of listed Industrial Goods companies in Nigeria. Therefore, this study sought to ask the following specific questions:

- i. What is the effect of audit committee financial expertise on earnings management of Nigeria's listed industrial goods companies?
- ii. What is the effect of audit committee meetings on earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria?

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of audit committee characteristics on earnings management of listed Industrial Goods companies in Nigeria.

The specific objectives are:

- i. To examine the effect of audit committee financial expertise on earnings management of Nigeria's listed industrial goods companies.
- ii. To examine the effect of audit committee meetings on earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Literature Review

This section reviews the different literature on audit committee characteristics and earnings management in respect to the conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical review. This sub-section discusses the concepts of audit committee characteristics such as audit committee financial expertise, audit committee meetings and earnings management.

The audit committee of a company is defined as "a committee appointed by the board of directors to act as a liaison between the board and the external auditors; this committee typically comprises of the majority of non-executive directors and is supposed to keep a distant and dispassionate view of the company's operations" (Habbash, 2010). The traits, makeup, and practices of the audit committee inside an organization are referred to as audit committee characteristics. The audit committee is a subcommittee of the board of directors in charge of reviewing the financial reporting process, internal controls, and audit activities (Appah & Appiah, 2011).

Audit Committee Financial Expertise are audit committees that are in charge of assessing and evaluating the organizational ethics climate, financial records, legislative compliance, institutional management, and information procedures. According to Gurusamy (2017), having the right individuals with the right degrees of knowledge can significantly improve a company's financial performance. Accounting errors can be avoided with the presence of an accounting or financial professional (Kallamu & Saat, 2015). Similarly, having financial specialists on the audit committee reduces conflicts between management and external auditors while also improving financial and non-financial reporting. The audit committee colleagues should undoubtedly have the necessary abilities and knowledge to carry out these responsibilities (Yahaya & Onyabe, 2022).

H₀₁: Audit committee financial expertise has no significant effect on earnings management of Nigeria's listed industrial goods companies.

Audit Committee Meetings is more vital than ever to hold regular audit committee meetings. Such gatherings could help to reduce the agency's difficulty and eliminate asymmetric data. If regular meetings are held, shareholders and all Investors may be able to obtain accurate and timely .data to facilitate effective financial decisions as a result, regular Audit Committee meetings are an important aspect that can have a significant impact on the financial success of a company. Morrissey (2011), for the Audit Committee, recommends four social problems in one year.

Core (2010) sets audit committees, which meet periodically to raise the clarity and receptivity of recorded revenue, and consequently to Improve the standard of income. To determine whether the regularity of meetings affects financial performance. In order to assess whether the frequency of meetings influences the excellence of financial statements, Guthrie and Turnbull (2014), used the number of meetings and found the favorable association. However, on the effect on the existence of the volatility of financial announcements by the meeting of the audit committee. Lin (2012), no association between periods and existence of financial-related detailing of repeated audit Committee meeting. The regulatory regime for which audit committees conduct meetings to administer monitoring and internal management systems is more likely to contribute to effective outcomes.

H₀₂: Audit committee meetings has no significant effect on earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Earnings management is defined as "a deliberate interference in the external reporting of finances process for the purpose of creating personal gain" by Schipper, (1989). Management is "earnings-managing" when it has the authority to influence reported income through accounting decisions (Roman, 2009). Earnings management, as defined by Healy and Wahlen, (1999), arises when managers exercise their discernment in financial reporting and transaction structuring to manipulate financial reports in order to mislead some stakeholders about the company's underlying economic performance or influence contractual outcomes that rely on

reported accounting principles.

Rahman et al., (2013) defined "earnings management" as the practice of "reasonable and lawful management decision making and reporting" with the purpose of delivering steady and predictable financial results. Considering the accounting profession's ethical principles and practices, this interpretation may no longer be valid. To determine materiality, information is considered relevant if its omission or distortion may have a significant influence on a user's capacity to make smart financial decisions. The Financial Accounting Standard Board (FASB), an X-ray of worldwide accounting standard-setters, defines materiality as the extent of an oversight or falsification of accounting data, when examined in conjunction with other criteria, raises the possibility that the company would break down.

Abdullahi (2022) investigates the effect of various audit committee characteristics and corporate performance in Bahrain. The effect of audit committee independence, size, and meeting frequency on company earnings (using ROE, ROA, and Tobin's Q) is investigated in this research. During 2005-2019, data from all intangible publicly listed businesses on the Bahrain Bourse were used. The findings revealed that organisations with independent audit committees and large audit committees perform ineffectively. It has also been demonstrated that the number of audit committee meetings has no effect on corporate performance.

Furthermore, no relationship was found between the number of audit committee meetings and corporate performance in this study. The results imply that shareholders might not understand the importance of corporate governance frameworks. A wide range of stakeholders, including investors, auditors, and regulators, should find the study's conclusions useful in their attempts to enhance business performance and assessment practices in developing nations.

Galal, Soliman, and Bekheit (2022) investigate the effect of Audit Committee Characteristics and Earnings Management: Evidence from Egyptian Stock Exchange Firms. The paper highlights the various contributions provided by each proxy and provides persuasive evidence demonstrating how an Audit Committee mechanism influences Earnings Management. The purpose of this research is to look at how the characteristics of the audit committee effect earnings management in Egypt. For the eight fiscal years from 2012 to 2019, a sample of 80 Egyptian non-financial enterprises registered on the Egyptian Stock Exchange was used.

Audit Committee 4 independence, Audit Committee size, the frequency of Audit Committee meetings, Audit Committee expertise, and Audit Committee gender are all examples of Audit Committee features. The purpose of this research is to look at how the characteristics of the audit committee effect earnings management in Egypt. For the eight fiscal years from 2012 to 2019, a sample of 80 Egyptian non-financial enterprises registered on the Egyptian Stock Exchange was used. Audit Committee independence, Audit Committee size, the frequency of Audit Committee meetings, Audit Committee expertise, and Audit Committee gender are all examples of Audit Committee features. Discretionary accruals are used as a proxy for Earnings Management. Panel data regression was used in the archival modeling study. Using a multiple regression model to evaluate the link between the variables, the findings show that Audit Committee Size, Audit Committee Expertise, and Audit Committee Gender have a significant negative effect on Earnings Management.

Furthermore, there is no significant relationship between Audit Committee Meetings and Earnings Management. Earnings Management and Audit Committee Independence have a favorable and significant link. This research makes multiple suggestions to Egypt's regulatory agencies on how to make improvements and strengthen firm internal governance systems, particularly the Audit Committee.

Williamson and Akpomedaye (2021) investigate the relationship between listed consumer product manufacturing companies in Nigeria's audit committee membership and earnings management. Using a sample of thirteen (13) listed consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria over an eight-year period (2012–2019), the study used an ex-post factor research methodology. The ordinary least square regression technique was applied to analyze a pool of panel data obtained from the publicly available annual reports of the selected companies. The study found a significant correlation between the audit committee composition and the earning management of the studied organizations at a 95% confidence level, the study discovered that audit committee composition has a substantial relationship with earning management of sampled firms.

According to the study, the structure of audit committees has a negative but noteworthy effect on the management of earnings for listed consumer goods manufacturers in Nigeria. Based on the results, recommendations were made to increase the number of independent non- executive members on the audit committee in order to decrease the incidence of earnings management and other representational errors. Additionally, it was suggested that the Nigerian code of corporate governance include a clause regarding the tenure of these members in order to reduce the risk of familiarity and enhance the caliber of financial reporting.

The effect of corporate governance on the earnings management of American corporations was also studied by Chtourou et al., (2001). They used data from Compustat 1996 to conclude that boards with more economic expertise, autonomous directors, and energetic committees (as measured by board consultations) have lower levels of discretionary accruals. Through this evaluation, we look at how well earnings management is functioning in light of actual accruals. Numerous studies have looked at how audit committees affect the quality of financial reporting, profitability, and audits, and how they can affect earnings management because of their central role in good corporate governance.

According to Hassan's (2011) an analysis of the relationship between corporate governance and the accuracy of financial statements, instituting stricter measures of governance has resulted in a marked improvement in the accuracy of financial reporting. The study employed several proxy indicators, one of which was the audit committee's own procedures. Baxter and Cotter, (2012) found that instituting an audit committee enhanced the quality of profits while reducing the need for intensive earnings management. In an effort to raise auditing criteria.

Halim (2021) looks into how financial distress avoidance is impacted by the size of the audit committee, the Independent Commissioner, and the shareholder equity ratio. In this study, the sizes of the Audit Committee, Independent Commissioners, Shareholder Equity (SHE) Ratio, and Financial Distress were determined using the Altman Z-Score Model. Public companies that were listed between 2015 and 2017 on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) were the subjects of the investigation. Purposive sampling was used to select these samples, and multiple regression analysis was used to analyze the secondary data, resulting in a total of 19 organizations that fit the criteria. The study's findings indicate that there was no beneficial correlation between financial hardship avoidance and the effectiveness of the audit committee, as determined by the committee's size and the number of Independent Commissioners. In the meantime, the SHE ratio significantly and favorably influences the alleviation of financial issues.

The efficacy of audit committees in restricting earnings management in Indian firms was examined by Manta (2021). A sample of 130 BSE-listed companies' secondary data is gathered, and it is assessed over the course of three years, from 2013 to 2015. Bi correlations, logistic regression models, and multivariate linear regression are used in empirical analysis. Research indicates that the number of directorships held by audit committee members, the size of the committee, and the frequency of audit committee meetings all significantly affect the quality of earnings. It has been demonstrated that additional audit committee characteristics have little bearing on earnings management. The study's conclusions offer crucial information that regulators and firm boards can use to assess the performance of board audit committees and implement additional governance measures to help safeguard the integrity of financial statements.

Theoretical Review

In the area of corporate governance and financial reporting, the impact of the audit committee and earnings management team utilizing agency theory is a fascinating and pertinent topic. Understanding this effect and any potential conflicts of interest that can develop is made easier with the help of agency theory Lin et al., (2006). Agency theory contends that because ownership and control are separated in contemporary organizations, there is an intrinsic conflict of interest between principals, or shareholders, and agents, or managers. Managers, as agents, may be tempted to engage in earnings management practices to portray a better financial performance and secure their own interests, such as higher compensation or job security, at the expense of shareholders' interests.

On behalf of the shareholders (principals), the audit committee, which is normally made up of independent directors, is responsible for keeping an eye on the financial reporting procedure and supervising the management's decisions. By guaranteeing the accuracy and dependability of financial accounts and preventing shady earnings management techniques, a strong audit committee can lessen the agency problem (Beasley & Salterio, 2001). Agency theory suggests that a strong and effective audit committee can help mitigate the agency problem by aligning management's reporting incentives with shareholders' interests, enhancing the credibility and reliability of financial statements, and reducing the potential for opportunistic earnings management practices.

Materials and Methods

The study uses an ex-post facto research strategy, this is because the data already existed and the researcher had no intention of manipulating any of the variables. As a result, ex-post facto design is selected since the study tries to discover the different between numerous independent variables and independent variables. The listed industrial products businesses in the Nigerian Exchange Group make up the study's population (NGXGROUP), This is because the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGXGROUP) is a multy - asset exchange providing a home to the best African businesses listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group. The listed industrial products firms as of 2021 are displayed in table 1.

Table 1: Population of the Study

No.	Industrial Goods	Years of Incorp.	Year of Listing
1	African Paints (Nigeria) Plc.	16/03/1974	30/06/1996
2	Austin Laz & Company Plc.		
3	Berger Paints Plc.	01/09/1959	
4	Beta Glass Co. Plc.	02/06/1974	02/07/1986
5	Cap Plc.		
6	Cement Co. of North. Nig. Plc	15/08/1962	04/10/1993
7	Cutix Plc.	04/11/1982	08/12/1987
8	Dangote Cement Plc.	17/02/2010	26/10/2010
9	First Aluminium Nigeria Plc.	20/08/1960	11/05/1992
10	Greif Nigeria Plc.		
11	Lafarge Africa Plc.	24/02/1959	
12	Meyer Plc.	20/05/1960	
13	Paints and Coatings Manufactures Plc.	16/03/2001	02/11/2010
14	Portland Paints & Products Nigeria Plc.	03/09/1985	09/07/2009
15	Premier Paints Plc.	24/08/1982	07/03/1995

Source: NGXGROUP daily listing (www.ngxgroup.com.ng), 2023

The convenient sampling technique was adopted for the purpose is this study, because it is a sampling strategy that involves selecting participant based on their accessibility and availability. Thus, taking a current data frequently yields enough data points to provide statistical confidence in the results (Cvent, 2019). However, a two-point filter was used, and in order to be included in the sample, a firm must have been listed in NGXGROUP before 2012 and must have issued financial reports throughout the study period. As indicated in table 2, the application of the criterion resulted in the selection of 9 companies as the study's sample size.

Table 2: Sample Size

No.	Industrial Goods	Years of Incorp.	Year of Listing
1	Berger Paints Plc.	01/09/1959	
2	Beta Glass Co. Plc.	02/06/1974	02/07/1986
3	Cap Plc.		
4	Dangote Cement Plc.	17/02/2010	26/10/2010
5	Greif Nigeria Plc.		
6	Lafarge Africa Plc.	24/02/1959	
7	Meyer Plc.	20/05/1960	
8	Portland Paints & Products Nigeria Plc.	03/09/1985	09/07/2009
9	Premier Paints Plc.	24/08/1982	07/03/1995

Source: Generated from table 1

Model Specification

The following is the model used to empirically test the hypotheses formulated. The adoption of this model was in line with the work of Nelson and Jamil (2011), Yang and Krishnan (2005) and Baxter and Cotter (2013).

$$EM = f(ACF, ACM, FSZ \& LEV)$$

$$EM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACF_{it} + \beta_2 ACM_{it} + \beta_3 FSZ_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + e$$

Where:

EM = Earnings management of Company *i* in year *t*

ACF = Audit committee financial expertise of Company *i* in year *t*

ACM = Audit committee meeting of Company *i* in year *t*

FSZ = Firm size of Company *i* in year *t*

LEV = Leverage of Company *i* in year *t*

β_0 = Is the constant (i.e., the intercept)

$\beta_1 = \beta_4$ = Is the coefficient of the independent variables (i.e., the slope)
 e = Error term
 i = Individual Company (9 firms)
 t = Time period (10years)

Variable and their Measurement

Table 3: Variable and their Measurement

Variables		Measurement
DV	Earnings Management (EM)	Measured by absolute values of the residuals (discretionary accruals) using Modified Jones model by Dechow et al. (1995).
IVs	Audit Committee Financial Expertise (ACF)	Proportion of audit committee members with financial expertise (financial knowledge) in the audit committee to total number of the audit committee
	Audit Committee Meetings (ACM)	The number of meetings held by the audit committee during the year
CV	Firm Size (FSZ)	A control variable measured as natural logarithm of the Firms total assets
	Leverage (LEV)	Leverage is measured as the ratio of debt to equity (DeFond & Francis, 2005)

Sources and Methods of Data Collection

This study used secondary source of data for the purpose of this work, which consist annual reports and accounts of the sampled company obtained for analysis. It consists of existing information which may be useful for the purpose of the study at hand. The secondary data will be sourced from the company's financial report for the period of 10 years from 2012 to 2021 contained in the company's annual reports. This period is considered appropriate because it fall within the period when Nigerian exchange group experienced a remarkable developmental-changes as well as improvement in the policy framework of corporate governance. This is in terms of its structure, operational activities and increase in the number of listed companies and securities. Also, this period is considered long enough for the variables to form a pattern in combination with the economic and financial activities of the industries. The method of data analysis for the study was multiple regression. The response variable (represented by an equation) of a relationship can be predicted using regression and parameters. In statistical analysis, diagnostic checks are methods used to evaluate a statistical model's validity and underlying assumptions.

Results and Discussion

This section analyses and empirically evaluates the information collected for the study. It starts by examining descriptive statistics and a correlation matrix. It then presents the results of the regression and reviews the findings in light of prior research studies. It concludes with a discussion of the policy implications of the findings.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics organize and compile the data in a way that is more relevant. The overview of the descriptive statistics for the variables are presented in table 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

VARIABLES	OBS	MEAN	STD. DEV.	MIN	MAX	KURTOSIS	SKEWNESS
EM	90	0.3048	0.2184	-0.05	0.399	0.3783	0.0005
ACF	90	0.9089	1.195	0.082	8.243	0.000	0.0000
ACM	90	3.7083	0.9444	2	5	0.0135	0.0000
FSZ	90	5.7920	0.8742	4	9	0.5829	0.0013
LEV	90	0.2130	0.3248	0.01	0.32	0.4451	0.0009

Source: STATA 2023.

Earnings management (EM) has a mean value of 0.3048 and a standard deviation value of 0.2184 which signifies that the data deviates from the mean by 0.2184. ROA has a minimum and maximum value of -0.05 and 0.399 respectively. EM has a Kurtosis value of 0.3783 and skewness value of 0.0005. Audit committee financial expertise (ACF) has a minimum and maximum value of 0.082 and 8.243 respectively. The average and standard deviation of ACF is 0.9089 and 1.195 which signifies high level of dispersion. ACF has a Kurtosis value of 0.000 and skewness value of 0.000.

Audit committee meeting (ACM) has an average value of 3.7083 and a standard deviation value of 0.9444 which signifies that the data deviates from the mean. The minimum and maximum value of ACM are 2 and 5 respectively. ACM has a Kurtosis value of 0.0135 and skewness value of 0.000. Firm size (FSZ) has a minimum and maximum value of 4 and 9 respectively. FSZ has a mean value of 5.7920 and a standard deviation value of 0.8742, this signifies that the data deviates from the mean. FSZ has a Kurtosis value of 0.5829 and skewness value of 0.0013. Leverage (LEV) has a minimum and maximum value of 0.01 and 0.32 respectively. LEV has a mean value of 0.2130 and a standard deviation value of 0.3248, this signifies that the data deviates from the mean. LEV has a Kurtosis value of 0.4451 and skewness value of 0.0009.

Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix explains the degree of relationship between the dependent and independent variables as well as the independent variables among themselves.

Table 5: Correlation Matrix

	EM	ACF	ACM	FSZ	LEV
EM	1				
ACF	0.3342	1			
ACM	0.6639	0.5762	1		
FSZ	0.1755	0.1369	0.1339	1	
LEV	0.4270	0.2489	0.3417	0.1312	1

Source: STATA, 2023

Audit committee financial expertise (ACF) has a positive association with earnings management (EM) of listed Industrial goods companies in Nigeria which can be observed from the computed values of coefficient of 0.3342. Audit committee meeting (ACM) has a positive association with earnings management (EM) which can be observed from the computed values of beta coefficient 0.6639, firm size (FSZ) have a positive association with earnings management (EM) of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria which can be

observed from the computed values of coefficient of 0.1755. Leverage (LEV) have a positive association with earnings management (EM) of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria which can be observed from the computed values of coefficient of 0.4270. The relationship between the independent variables between themselves reveals that firm size (FSZ) and audit committee financial expertise (ACF) have a positive association amongst themselves. Also, audit committee meeting (ACM) and audit committee financial expertise (ACF) has a positive association among themselves. Leverage (LEV) and audit committee financial expertise (ACF) have a positive association amongst themselves.

Also, Audit committee meeting (ACM) and firm size (FSZ) has a positive association among themselves. Also, Audit committee meeting (ACM) and leverage (LEV) has a positive association. While, Also, leverage (LEV) and firm size (FSZ) has a positive association among themselves. The multicollinearity test reveals a tolerant value variance inflation factor of loss 1 and 10 respectively. That is, an instance in which two or more explanatory variables in a multiple regression model are highly linearly related is referred to as a situation with a high linear relationship. This specifies the absent of multicollinearity problem associated with the data of the study. Also, the VIF test for heteroskedacity shows a Chi2 value of 39.06 with the corresponding P-value of 0.000 which statistically significant at 1% level of significant. This signifies the non-existence of heteroskedastic problem associated with the data of the study. Also, it was necessary to test for fixed and random effect models and then Hausman test in order to decide between fixed and random effect model which one is to be adopted for the study. The result of Hausman test reveals a Chi2 value of 0.4308 p-value of 0.0000 which is significant at 1% level of significant. This means GLS fixed effect model is best regression result for the study, as such the study adopted GLS fixed effect regression model.

Table 6: GLS Fixed Effect Regression

	CO-EFFICIENT	T-VALUES	P-VALUES	TOLERANCE VALUE	V.I.F
CONSTANT	0.816	6.11	0.000		
ACF	0.147	1.98	0.046		1.51
ACM	0.734	5.16	0.000		1.50
FSZ	0.798	2.20	0.032		1.02
LEV	0.2319	2.04	0.037		1.06
R ²	0.4527				
Adjusted R ²	0.4372				
F-STATISTICS		29.23			
F-SIGNIFICANCE			0.0000		

SOURCE: STATA 2023

$$EM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACF_{it} + \beta_2 ACM_{it} + \beta_3 FSZ_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Table 6 above shows R2 value of 0.4527 which signifies that 45% of the total variation of profitability of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria caused by the combined effect of ACF, ACM, FSZ and LEV in the model of this study. The F-Statistics of the model stood at 29.23 with p-value of 0.0000 which is significant at 1% level of significant. This signifies that the model of the study is well fitted with the variables of the study.

Audit Committee Financial Expertise (ACF) and Earnings Management (EM)

The table 6 shows that there is a positive and significant impact between ACF and EM of industrial goods companies in Nigeria. This can be seen by the computed value of beta coefficient of 0.147 with the corresponding P-value of 0.046 which is significant at 5%. There

is a positive and significant relationship between ACF and EM of industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The result of this study is not in line with the findings of Velnampy (2012).

Audit Committee Meetings (ACM) and Earnings Management (EM)

The table 6 shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between ACM and EM of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. This can be observed by the computed value of beta coefficient of 0.734 with the corresponding P-value of 0.000 which is significant at 5% level of significant. Therefore, there is positive and significant relationship between ACM and EM of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The result of this study is in line with the findings of Salawu (2009), Oke and Babatunde (2011), but it contradicts the findings of Olokoyo (2012).

Firm Size (FSZ) and Earnings Management (EM)

The table 6 shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between FSZ and EM of listed industrial companies in Nigeria. This can be shown by the computed value of beta coefficient of 0.798 with the corresponding P-value of 0.032 that is significant. Therefore, there is a positive and significant relationship between FSZ and EM in Nigeria. The finding of the study is in line with the result of Salimand Yadav (2012) and it contradicts the findings of Luper and Isaac (2012) and Tailab (2014).

Leverage (LEV) and Earnings Management (EM)

The table 6 shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between LEV and EM of listed industrial companies in Nigeria. This can be shown by the computed value of beta coefficient of 0.2319 with the corresponding P-value of 0.037 that is significant. Therefore, there is a positive and significant relationship between LEV and EM in Nigeria. The finding of the study is in line with the result of Roman (2009) and Onyabe, et al., (2018).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Emanating from the data collected and the tests of the research hypotheses, the study concludes that Audit committee significantly affect earnings management in listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. However, specifically the study concludes as thus;

Audit committee size significantly affects earnings management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria from the findings of the study. On the other hand, audit committee financial expertise significantly influences earnings management positively. Meanwhile, audit committee meetings equally depict positive effect on earnings management of Nigeria listed industrial goods businesses.

Based on the findings, the study recommends the followings;

1. The management of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria should engage expertise audit members who have specific knowledge and expertise relevant to financial reporting, auditing, and internal controls in order to improve the firms' earning structure and overall performance of the firm.
2. The management of Nigerian listed industrial goods companies should hold regular meetings to oversee the financial reporting process, internal controls, and the audit function within an organisation.
3. The management of Nigeria's listed industrial goods companies should enhance the size of their firms since it has the ability to increase the earnings of Nigeria's listed industrial goods firms.

4. Nigeria's listed industrial goods companies should monitor of their firms leverage since it has the ability to increase the earnings of Nigeria's listed industrial goods firms.

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